

Reactivity Balance Equation to Estimate Reactivity Coefficients of Sodium-Cooled Fast Reactor by Measurable Parameters under Power Change Events

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ABSTRACT

A reactivity balance equation was derived to measure the reactivity coefficients of a sodium-cooled fast reactor considering reactor power variation. The formulation incorporates thermal feedback from fuel, coolant, cladding and structural expansion, and distinguishes between contributions from power changes and from inlet temperature variations. Conventional approaches, such as isothermal temperature or power coefficient measurements, often mix the Doppler and coolant temperature effects, making it difficult to evaluate each coefficient independently. The proposed balance equation provides a systematic framework that directly relates measurable reactor responses to individual coefficients, thereby providing a practical basis for separating and measuring them in experiments. To examine applicability, numerical calculations were performed for the sodium-cooled fast reactor Monju. The Doppler and coolant temperature coefficients were estimated simultaneously using a least-squares method with Monte Carlo sampling to evaluate confidence intervals. The reference values were obtained from calculation results using FRBurner code. The estimated values were generally consistent with reference values, although a slight positive bias and reduced stability were observed due to strong correlations among variables. These results demonstrate that the reactivity balance approach can provide a practical framework for measurement of reactivity coefficients, and that conditions involving both power and inlet temperature variations are expected to improve estimation accuracy.

Keywords: Sodium-cooled fast reactor, Reactivity balance, Reactivity coefficient, Measurement

1. INTRODUCTION

The fuel Doppler effect and the thermal expansion of fuel, coolant, and structural materials are important safety indices in fast reactors. These effects are commonly represented by reactivity coefficients, including the Doppler coefficient, coolant temperature coefficient, and expansion reactivity [1–3]. Proper evaluation of these coefficients is essential for characterizing the neutronic behavior of the core. However, experimental determination is challenging because measured reactivity changes generally include contributions from multiple feedback mechanisms. For example, in conventional measurements of the isothermal temperature coefficient (ITC) or the power coefficient, both the Doppler and coolant temperature coefficients contribute simultaneously, making it difficult to identify each coefficient independently. Furthermore, reactivity coefficients depend on the spatial distribution of temperature changes. The ITC is obtained by increasing the coolant inlet temperature so that the average core temperature rises uniformly, thereby involving both Doppler and coolant temperature effects. In contrast, during power variation, the temperature distribution is spatially non-uniform, leading to differences from the coefficients derived under isothermal conditions. These differences must be recognized when evaluating core neutronic characteristics.

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Several approaches have been explored to overcome these limitations. In Monju, a multivariable measurement technique was proposed to separate the contributions from power-induced effects and inlet temperature variations [4]. This method enabled simultaneous evaluation of two composite coefficients, denoted as KR (power-induced) and Kin (inlet-temperature-induced), but it did not provide a direct measurement of the Doppler coefficient. In light water reactors, Demazière and Pázsit demonstrated that neutron noise analysis could be used to estimate the moderator temperature coefficient (MTC) non-invasively during steady-state operation [5]. This approach is attractive for continuous monitoring but cannot isolate the Doppler effect. In addition, inverse estimation techniques based on extended Kalman filtering have been applied for CANDU reactors to estimate the Doppler, moderator, and structural feedback coefficients [6]. While these data assimilation methods can provide online estimates, they rely on dynamic models to reconstruct changes in fuel and moderator temperatures, and their accuracy is sensitive to model errors. These studies highlight the difficulty of experimentally separating reactivity coefficients associated with different physical feedback mechanisms.

In the present study, a reactivity balance equation is formulated to directly connect measurable reactor responses with individual reactivity coefficients in a sodium-cooled fast reactor. The basic principle can be traced back to the reactivity balance approach introduced by Wade and Fujita [7], where an exact balance is established between inserted reactivity and negative feedback following a power change. Similar concepts have recently been applied to criteria for preventing fuel melting during unprotected transient overpower (UTOP) events [8]. Building upon this framework, the proposed expression is designed for experimental application and enables the explicit evaluation of the Doppler and coolant temperature coefficients without relying on the estimation of temperature changes in individual core materials. In this formulation, it is assumed that the initial average temperatures of core materials (e.g., coolant temperature under nominal conditions) are known, and that measurable variations such as coolant inlet temperature changes are available. This simplification makes the method more practical for experimental implementation. The differences between coefficients obtained under power variation and those under uniform heating are also clarified. The feasibility of applying the proposed approach is preliminarily examined through trial calculations under simplified conditions.

2. FORMULATION OF REACTIVITY BALANCE EQUATION

In order to evaluate reactivity coefficients from experimental conditions where reactor power varies, it is necessary to formulate a reactivity balance that explicitly incorporates the major feedback mechanisms. These include temperature rises in coolant, fuel, and cladding, as well as dimensional changes such as axial and radial expansions of fuel pins and the expansion of the support plate. The wrapper tube expansion is omitted from consideration in this study for simplicity. The following subsections derive the expressions step by step, with the assumption that the spatial power distribution remains essentially unchanged during the transient. This assumption allows the results to be expressed in terms of the normalized power ratio and the inlet coolant temperature variation.

2.1. Reactivity Introduced by Coolant Temperature Change

At asymptotic equilibrium, the coolant temperature at height z is expressed as

$$T_c(z) = T_{c,in} + \frac{\int_0^z q(z') dz'}{W c_p}, \quad (1)$$

where $T_{c,in}$ is the inlet coolant temperature, $q(z')$ is the local volumetric power density, W is the coolant mass flow rate, and c_p is the specific heat. At the reference state (before perturbation), the corresponding expression is

$$T_{c,0}(z) = T_{c,in,0} + \frac{\int_0^z q_0(z') dz'}{W_0 c_p}. \quad (2)$$

Assuming that the normalized power distribution remains unchanged, the ratio of integrated reactor power P' is

$$P' = \frac{P}{P_0} = \frac{\int_0^Z q(z') dz'}{\int_0^Z q_0(z') dz'} \quad (3)$$

We set $W = W_0$ since flow rate changes are neglected in the present study. Thus, using Eq. (3), the coolant temperature difference between perturbed and reference states can be expressed as

$$T_c(z) - T_c(0) = (P' - 1) (T_{c,0}(z) - T_{c,0}(0)). \quad (4)$$

The change in the average coolant temperature is then

$$\bar{T}_c - \bar{T}_{c,0} = (P' - 1)(\bar{T}_{c,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \Delta T_{c,in}, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta T_{c,in} = T_{c,in} - T_{c,in,0}$. Here, the first term corresponds to heating induced by power increase, while the second term corresponds to heating due to the inlet temperature rise. The reactivity associated with coolant temperature change is expressed using distinct coefficients for power-driven and inlet-driven contributions:

$$\rho_c(t) = M_c^P (P' - 1)(\bar{T}_{c,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + M_c^{ISO} \Delta T_{c,in}, \quad (6)$$

where M_c^P is the coolant temperature reactivity coefficient defined for temperature rise induced by core power increase, and M_c^{ISO} is the corresponding coefficient for uniform (isothermal) temperature rise caused by inlet coolant heating.

2.2. Reactivity Introduced by Fuel Temperature Change

In the present model, it is assumed that the heat transfer characteristics between fuel and coolant remain unchanged, and that the shape of the power distribution is preserved before and after the perturbation. Under these assumptions, for each fuel type k , the average fuel temperature in the equilibrium state can be expressed as the sum of a power-driven contribution and an inlet-temperature-driven contribution:

$$\bar{T}_{f,k} - \bar{T}_{f,k,0} = (P' - 1)(\bar{T}_{f,k,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \Delta T_{c,in}. \quad (7)$$

Similar to Eq. (5), the first term is induced by power increase, and the second term is due to the inlet temperature rise. The increase in the average fuel temperature contributes to several types of reactivity feedback. One is the axial thermal expansion reactivity of the fuel and expressed as

$$\rho_{f,k,ex,z} = M_{f,k,ex,z}^P (P' - 1)(\bar{T}_{f,k,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + M_{f,k,ex,z}^{ISO} \Delta T_{c,in}. \quad (8)$$

The subscript “ex” represents “expansion” in this paper. Another reactivity effect arises from the Doppler feedback, which is considered to be proportional to the logarithm of the ratio of the averaged fuel temperature before and after the perturbation:

$$\rho_D(t) \propto \ln \left(\frac{\bar{T}_{f,k}}{\bar{T}_{f,k,0}} \right). \quad (9)$$

The logarithmic term can be decomposed into contributions associated with inlet temperature rise and with power increase. By substituting Eq. (7), the following relation is obtained:

$$\frac{\bar{T}_{f,k}}{\bar{T}_{f,k,0}} = \frac{\bar{T}_{f,k,0} + \Delta T_{c,in}}{\bar{T}_{f,k,0}} \cdot \frac{\bar{T}_{f,k,0} + (P' - 1)(\bar{T}_{f,k,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \Delta T_{c,in}}{\bar{T}_{f,k,0} + \Delta T_{c,in}}. \quad (10)$$

The first factor on the right-hand side corresponds to the contribution from the inlet temperature rise, while the second factor represents the contribution from the power increase. Accordingly, the Doppler reactivity can be expressed as

$$\rho_D(t) = M_{D,k}^{ISO} \ln \left(\frac{\bar{T}_{f,k,0} + \Delta T_{c,in}}{\bar{T}_{f,k,0}} \right) + M_{D,k}^P \ln \left(\frac{\bar{T}_{f,k,0} + (P' - 1)(\bar{T}_{f,k,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \Delta T_{c,in}}{\bar{T}_{f,k,0} + \Delta T_{c,in}} \right). \quad (11)$$

Here, $M_{D,k}^{ISO}$ denotes the Doppler reactivity coefficient with respect to the isothermal temperature rise caused by inlet coolant heating, and $M_{D,k}^P$ represents the coefficient associated with the non-uniform fuel temperature increase due to power change.

2.3. Reactivity Introduced by Cladding Temperature Change and Support Plate Expansion

Similarly, assuming that the heat transfer conditions remain unchanged, the averaged cladding temperature change can be expressed as

$$\overline{T}_{cl}(t) - \overline{T}_{cl}(0) = (P' - 1)(\overline{T}_{cl,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \Delta T_{c,in}. \quad (12)$$

The corresponding reactivity feedback arises from the expansion of the cladding, which modifies the core geometry. This contribution is expressed as

$$\rho_{cl,ex,z}(t) = M_{cl,ex}^P(P' - 1)(\overline{T}_{cl,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + M_{cl,ex}^{ISO}\Delta T_{c,in}, \quad (13)$$

where $M_{cl,ex}^P$ denotes the reactivity coefficient for cladding expansion induced by power-dependent heating, and $M_{cl,ex}^{ISO}$ represents the coefficient corresponding to expansion caused by a uniform temperature rise due to inlet coolant heating.

The support plate expansion is modeled as proportional to the inlet coolant temperature change:

$$\rho_{sup,ex,r} = M_{sup,ex,r}^{ISO}\Delta T_{c,in}. \quad (14)$$

2.4. Reactivity Balance Equation

At asymptotic equilibrium, the reactivity balance is given by

$$\rho_{total} + \rho_{ext} = 0. \quad (15)$$

Here, ρ_{total} is the sum of all feedback reactivity and ρ_{ext} is the external reactivity. The total reactivity is the sum of the individual contributions:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{total} = & \left(M_c^P(\overline{T}_{c,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \sum_k M_{f,k,ex,z}^P(\overline{T}_{f,k,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + M_{cl,ex}^P(\overline{T}_{cl,0} - T_{c,in,0}) \right) (P' - 1) \\ & + \left(M_c^{ISO} + \sum_k M_{f,k,ex,z}^{ISO} + M_{cl,ex}^{ISO} + M_{sup,ex,r}^{ISO} \right) \Delta T_{c,in} + \sum_k M_{D,k}^{ISO} \ln \left(\frac{\overline{T}_{f,k,0} + \Delta T_{c,in}}{\overline{T}_{f,k,0}} \right) \\ & + \sum_k M_{D,k}^P \ln \left(\frac{\overline{T}_{f,k,0} + (P' - 1)(\overline{T}_{f,k,0} - T_{c,in,0}) + \Delta T_{c,in}}{\overline{T}_{f,k,0} + \Delta T_{c,in}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

This formulation demonstrates that the feedback reactivity can be decomposed into power-dependent and inlet-temperature-dependent contributions from coolant, fuel, cladding, and support plate. It also indicates the limitation that, under inlet temperature perturbations, only the sum of the corresponding coefficients can be identified. In addition, since the Doppler reactivity contains nonlinear components with respect to fuel temperature, varying the inlet temperature may allow partial extraction of this nonlinear contribution. In Eq. (16), $\overline{T}_{f,k,0}$, $\overline{T}_{c,0}$, and $\overline{T}_{cl,0}$ needs to be estimated in advance based on design or reference conditions. The reactor power P' , $T_{c,in,0}$, and $\Delta T_{c,in}$ can be measured and are used to estimate the reactivity coefficients.

3. NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

This section presents trial calculations for estimating the core-wide Doppler coefficient and coolant temperature coefficient. The calculation conditions and methods are briefly described, and the obtained results are discussed in comparison with reference values.

3.1. Calculation Conditions

3.1.1. Neutronic and Thermal–Hydraulic Calculation Methods

Numerical calculations were performed for the sodium-cooled fast reactor Monju. The neutronic model employed a two-dimensional R–Z diffusion approximation with homogenized assemblies. Multigroup cross sections were prepared using the FRBurner [9] code based on the JENDL-4.0 [10] nuclear data library with a 70-group structure. The reference state was defined at 100% rated power (714 MW thermal) with the coolant mass flow rate of 3893.2 kg/s. Since this study focuses on the estimation of the core-wide Doppler coefficient and coolant temperature coefficient, the coolant inlet temperature was fixed at 670.15 K, and core structural expansion was not considered. The fuel compositions are summarized in Table I.

Fuel, cladding, and coolant temperatures were evaluated by simplified thermal–hydraulic calculations. The linear heat generation rate obtained from the neutronic calculation was used as input for temperature distribution analysis. The cladding temperature and fuel internal temperature were obtained by solving the heat conduction equation with a convective boundary condition imposed at the coolant interface. In principle, accurate evaluation of temperature distributions requires iterative coupling between neutronic and thermal–hydraulic calculations. However, since the objective of this study is limited to the estimation of reactivity coefficients, iterative calculations were not performed, including the reference state.

To obtain the reference values of the reactivity coefficients, preliminary thermal–hydraulic calculations were performed at the nominal condition and at a + 10% power perturbation defined relative to the base power level of each evaluated case. Two neutronic calculations were then carried out. One used the nominal temperature distribution, and the other replaced only the fuel or coolant temperature distribution with that from the 10% higher power case, while all other materials were kept at the nominal state. The difference in the effective multiplication factors between these two cases was taken as the reference reactivity coefficient.

Table I. Fuel Compositions

Item	Core fuel assemblies	Blanket fuel assemblies
Fuel material	MOX	UO ₂
Fissile Pu enrichment (wt%)	16 / 21 (inner / outer core)	–
Pu isotopic composition (wt%)	Pu ²³⁸ /Pu ²³⁹ /Pu ²⁴⁰ /Pu ²⁴¹ /Pu ²⁴² /Am ²⁴¹ =3.0 / 52.0 / 27.0 / 9.5 / 7.0 / 1.5	–
U ²³⁵ enrichment in U (wt%)	0.3	0.3

3.1.2. Estimation of Reactivity Coefficients using Reactivity Balance

The reactivity coefficients were estimated from the differences in reactivity between the 100% power condition and the reduced-power cases at 90% and 80%. Calculations were carried out at flow rates of 100%, 90%, and 80%, and the results from all these flow conditions were combined in a single regression to simultaneously estimate the coolant temperature coefficient (M_c^P) and the whole-core Doppler coefficient (M_D^P). The reactivity balance employed in this study is expressed as

$$\rho_{ij} = M_c^P x_{c,ij} + M_D^P x_{f,ij}, \quad (17)$$

where, $x_{c,ij}$ and $x_{f,ij}$ are the coefficient corresponding to the coolant temperature and Doppler terms in Eq. (16) for power i and flow rate j , respectively. For the estimation, data from all flow rates and power points were stacked to form the matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{c,11} & x_{f,11} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{c,ij} & x_{f,ij} \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{y} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{11} \\ \vdots \\ \rho_{ij} \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{m} = \begin{pmatrix} M_C^P \\ M_D^P \end{pmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

and the coefficients were obtained by solving the least-squares problem

$$\min_m \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{y}\|^2. \quad (19)$$

To account for uncertainties in the measured and calculated reactivity values, a Monte Carlo sampling approach was applied by adding Gaussian noise to the reactivity values (\mathbf{y}), with a standard deviation of 1% of $|\mathbf{y}|$. Using 10^4 samples, confidence intervals of the estimated coefficients M_C^P and M_D^P were evaluated.

3.2. Results and Discussion

The Doppler and coolant temperature coefficients were estimated using the multiplication factors. Table II shows the estimated means and their 95% confidence intervals (CIs), evaluated by Monte Carlo sampling with a 1% standard-deviation noise added to the reactivity data. Note that the 95% CIs represent the uncertainty of the estimated coefficients under the assumed noise model, and they do not indicate ranges for the reference values themselves. The reference values were obtained from FRBurner calculations. Table II shows the reference Doppler coefficient (-1.40×10^{-2}) lies within the 95% CI of the estimated Doppler coefficient (-1.45×10^{-2} to -1.16×10^{-2}). Likewise, the reference coolant temperature coefficient (3.22×10^{-6}) lies within the 95% CI of the estimated coolant coefficient (1.66×10^{-6} to 1.53×10^{-5}).

Compared with the reference values, the estimated means show a slight positive bias. In addition, even though the noise level was set conservatively at a standard deviation of only 1%, CIs of the estimated coefficients are relatively wide. This reduced stability of the estimation can be attributed to the fact that the explanatory variables $x_{c,ij}$ and $x_{f,ij}$ in Eq. (17) exhibit strong correlation, making it inherently difficult to decouple the Doppler and coolant temperature effects. In this analysis, the correlation coefficient reached 0.974.

As seen from Eq. (16), the Doppler reactivity also depends on the inlet coolant temperature variation $\Delta T_{c,in}$. Therefore, a promising way to improve the estimation accuracy is to design conditions in which both the coolant inlet temperature and reactor power are varied simultaneously.

Table II. Estimated and Reference Values of Reactivity Coefficients

Coefficient	Estimated mean	95% Confidence interval	Reference value
Doppler coefficient (T/dk/dT)	-1.30×10^{-2}	-1.45×10^{-2} to -1.16×10^{-2}	-1.40×10^{-2}
Coolant temperature coefficient (dk/k/dT)	8.36×10^{-6}	1.66×10^{-6} to 1.53×10^{-5}	3.22×10^{-6}

4. CONCLUSIONS

A reactivity balance equation was formulated to enable measurement of reactivity coefficients under power variation. Trial calculations for the Monju reactor showed that the Doppler and coolant temperature coefficients can be estimated simultaneously, with results generally consistent with reference values. A slight positive bias and reduced stability were observed due to strong correlations among variables. These findings indicate that the proposed balance equation provides a practical framework for experimental evaluation of reactivity coefficients, and that improved test conditions may further enhance estimation reliability.

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